

Quantifying generative AI chatbot quality: Lessons from Brazil

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Across sectors and continents, organisations deploying public-facing generative AI tools are facing a similar question: how do we know they’re working as intended, for the benefit of end users?

For Madalena Alves dos Santos, from the Department of Digital Transformation for the state of Rio de Janeiro in Brazil, this question became a shared project, thanks to the opportunities for collaboration provided by *The Turing Way* Practitioners Hub. Madalena and fellow Expert-in-Residence Ingrid Folland, CEO of AI solutions company [Japeto AI](#), have been working together to bring more rigour and accountability to Rio’s citizen-facing AI chatbot systems.

Reliability and safety: a shared concern

Madalena says: “We were discussing our chatbot project in one of the Practitioners Hub meetings – I said I was concerned about its accuracy and safety, and that we didn’t have a good way to measure those things. Ingrid mentioned she too had an interest in this topic and was working on something similar at Japeto, and that’s how the collaboration began.”

Ingrid adds: “There’s a recurring issue with generative AI – it’s useful, but how do you measure and evaluate it? At Japeto we had a basic method for reviewing chatbot conversations, but it wasn’t grounded in real data. So when Madalena and I connected through the Practitioners Hub and I heard about the project in Rio state, it felt like a great opportunity to build something better together.”

This case study outlines how the cross-organisational team addressed the initial question of how the accuracy of a generative AI-based chatbot can be evaluated, in the context of Rio’s prototype chatbot to help citizens access essential government services. Based on a large-scale test involving real users and subsequent analysis by human reviewers, the team developed an evaluation model to measure chatbot accuracy. In high-stakes scenarios such as governmental applications or health-related contexts, incorrect or hallucinatory responses can have serious consequences for the users of AI tools.

“Hallucination is a big risk,” says Ingrid. “If a chatbot gives wrong information in a confident tone,

users can't tell that it's wrong – and if it's a government chatbot, people are more likely to trust it. That's a serious responsibility.”

Madalena agrees: “We're very focused on safety because we've seen cases during testing where chatbots give inaccurate answers like hallucinating the wrong address for a hospital. That kind of mistake can really affect someone's life. Governments exist to make people's lives better, and we believe AI can help us serve citizens more effectively – but only if it's done responsibly.”

Addressing the challenge

The approach chosen to address this challenge consisted of the following steps:

Creating the chatbot prototype

The state of Rio de Janeiro has developed a chatbot to help citizens navigate and access public services more easily. The state's service platform, Portal RJ Digital, available via the [state website](#), consolidates over 2,500 public services from various agencies including healthcare, education, and social assistance. Through the portal, citizens can apply for a National Civil Identity document, check their child's school grades, pay taxes, file a police report, or retrieve medical test results, among other services.

One of the biggest usability challenges is that citizens must accurately describe the service they need, which can make it difficult to find the right option. To solve this issue, Rio's digital transformation team developed a chatbot prototype that allows users to describe their problem in simple terms. The chatbot then identifies the relevant service and provides a direct link, making it easier for citizens to access the information they need without struggling to navigate the portal.

The current version of the chatbot prototype operates based on a dataset containing information about the public services available on Portal RJ Digital. When a user submits a query, the chatbot searches this dataset to identify and recommend the most relevant service to the citizen. After receiving a response, the user has the option to evaluate its usefulness by selecting a like or dislike button, providing immediate feedback on the chatbot's performance.

Technical specifications of the chatbot

The chatbot's prototype code implements an AI-based system designed to assist citizens in finding public services on Portal RJ Digital. It uses OpenAI's API for natural language processing and integrates LangChain to structure user interactions. Conversations are stored in JSON files, allowing for tracking and analysis. To efficiently retrieve services, the system incorporates FAISS, a vector search engine that compares user queries with an embedded database of public services. Additionally, an interpretation agent reformulates user queries when necessary to improve search results.

The chatbot is deployed via Flask, exposing endpoints for interaction through HTTP requests. The main workflow begins with an initial search using FAISS. If no relevant service is found, the interpretation agent reformulates the query and performs another search. Users can provide feedback by rating responses with like and dislike buttons, helping to refine the chatbot's accuracy over time.

Creating an API for test data collection

Japeto has previously created a chatbot platform called Japeto Chat that allows clients to build, manage, and track analytics for their chatbots. The success of this collaborative project relied on being able to collect data from the Rio team's chatbot and load it into the Japeto Chat system to track analytics and signals.

To accomplish this, the team created an interface known as a REST API that could send data (including metadata) to the Japeto Chat dashboard as it was collected, where it is stored and then analysed.

Collected data included:

- the user's message
- the chatbot's response
- cosine value (that is, the similarity of the chatbot's answer to the correct or expected answer)
- user feedback (did they like or dislike the chatbot's response?)

While personal data is not collected in this version of the chatbot, that may not be the case for future versions – which would pose another set of ethical and safety risks, but may also provide further insights into how to improve the service. These trade offs must be finely balanced to retain public trust in the product.

Testing the chatbot

To assess the chatbot's accuracy, it was considered important to conduct tests with real users who shared characteristics with the intended audience. Internal testing by developers might not fully reflect how the chatbot would be used in practice, as their interactions could differ significantly from real-world scenarios. The goal was to expose the chatbot to questions similar to those it would likely receive after deployment.

Given the diverse population of the state of Rio de Janeiro, conducting testing in a public space with high footfall and a broad mix of social backgrounds seemed ideal. Central do Brasil – a major transport hub in the city of Rio de Janeiro – was chosen as the location. With thousands of people passing through daily, it is an excellent environment to gather insights from a wide range of users.

This prototype was tested in person at Central do Brasil from 17 to 21 February 2025. Passersby were invited to participate in the test using laptop computers. More than 500 people took part, resulting in approximately 700 conversations. The participants represented a diverse audience, and it was observed that spelling and grammar errors were common in user queries. This finding reinforced the importance of a chatbot capable of understanding sentences with grammatical mistakes.

Additionally, a remote testing link was made available to a network of micro-entrepreneurs from the Brazilian Service of Support for Micro and Small Enterprises (Sebrae), though only a small sample of tests was conducted this way.

Reviewing and assessing the collected test data

After testing, the chatbot’s responses were reviewed by human evaluators from Rio’s digital transformation team. Although the chatbot prototype includes like and dislike buttons for users to rate each response, a subsequent human review by civil servants was considered necessary. This is because user frustration does not always indicate an inaccuracy in the chatbot’s response.

In many cases, for example, users search for services provided by a different level of government, such as municipal services, which are not included in the Portal RJ Digital database. In such instances, the chatbot returns a standard response indicating that the requested service could not be found. While this may frustrate users, it does not constitute a technical inaccuracy.

Madalena adds: “Public services are complex – some are run by the state, others by municipalities or the federal government. But from the citizen’s perspective, that complexity doesn’t matter. The chatbot needs to serve them, regardless of whose responsibility it technically is.”

Human reviewers assessed the chatbot’s responses based on three criteria:

- **Quality:** analysis of the overall interaction, considering factors beyond simply the suggested services (such as clarity and coherence in the chatbot’s responses).
- **Accuracy:** assessing whether the chatbot correctly matched the user’s query to a service available in the provided dataset. This criterion verified if the chatbot retrieved the correct information from the dataset without generating incorrect or misleading responses.
- **Relevance:** evaluating whether the suggested service was useful and appropriate for the citizen’s request.

Next steps: Developing an evaluation model for chatbot accuracy

The aim of this project was to develop a stronger evaluation model for AI chatbots – possibly through a ‘health score’ to track performance over time. While it has not been possible to produce a definitive score from this project alone, the team has been able to extract valuable signals by analysing collected data (including user feedback and human reviews) with the help of an external statistician. The relevance, accuracy, and quality of chatbot answers were closely correlated, suggesting that asking just one well-designed question could be a good proxy for a more complex review in the future. Other findings included some instances of hallucination, such as a small number of invalid links, and a warning that while user feedback data is helpful, it should be treated with caution.

Through this exercise, the Japeto team now has a clearer path towards a general methodology for evaluating a chatbot’s performance, and may be able to compare accuracy levels between the OpenAI-based Rio tool and other LLMs. The digital transformation team in Rio, meanwhile, will refine its public service chatbot based on the findings obtained through testing and subsequent data analysis. After official deployment to public audiences, the agency will monitor the chatbot’s accuracy to continuously improve its quality, using the methodology developed alongside Japeto.

Key takeaways

- Chatbots and other AI-based products can provide a meaningful augmentation to existing public service resources, and help citizens navigate complex service archi-

teatures, as long as users can trust the output

- Key issues for developing government services chatbots include minimising hallucinations in responses through retrieval augmented generation, and developing an evaluation framework that balances actionable insights with public trust
- Public user testing by potential future users not only provides useful insights into the initial performance of prototype government chatbots, but is also a mechanism for citizen engagement with new technology
- Developing an overall 'health score' for chatbot evaluation is not straightforward, but even collecting limited user feedback can provide actionable insights
- Future evaluation of government services chatbots is a continuous process out of necessity, to monitor for quality and safety of responses, and overall user satisfaction with the service

Expert in Residence Spotlight: Madalena Alves dos Santos

Madalena Alves is a civil servant, currently serving as the Superintendent of Data and Results Management at the Department of Digital Transformation of the State of Rio de Janeiro. In her role, she coordinates activities related to digital and data strategy, open data, data analysis, and AI. She holds a Master's degree in Civil Law from the University of the State of Rio de Janeiro. Madalena believes that data and AI can play a significant role in improving people's lives.

Expert in Residence Spotlight: Ingrid Folland

Ingrid Folland is the CEO of Japeto, with a strong commitment to "tech for good." Starting in R&D, Ingrid transitioned into product design, development, and project management. Her focus at Japeto is on creating safe AI solutions for healthcare, education, and charitable organizations. Ingrid is passionate about using technology to make a positive impact on local communities.

Expert in Residence Spotlight: José Hudson

José Hudson is the Data and Intelligence Coordinator at the Secretariat of Digital Transformation of Rio de Janeiro (SETD). With a first degree in Public Administration and currently pursuing a degree in Computer Science, he focuses on data integration and implementing intelligence solutions to optimize public services in the state of Rio de Janeiro. His work involves leading initiatives that drive digital transformation within the public sector, ensuring that decisions are increasingly data-driven and evidence-based.

Expert in Residence Spotlight: Beatriz Gomes de Souza

Beatriz graduated in Public Management for Economic and Social Development from the Institute of Research in Urban and Regional Planning of the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro (GPDES/IPPUR/UFRJ) in 2023. She is currently a master's student in Population, Territory and Public Statistics at the National School of Statistical Sciences of the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (ENCE/IBGE). Beatriz is a public servant at the State Secretariat for

Digital Transformation, holding the position of Assistant to the Data Management and Intelligence Coordination.

Expert in Residence Spotlight: Jamie Tidman

Jamie Tidman is the CTO of Japeto, overseeing the technical direction of all projects with a focus on generative AI use cases. With a background in traditional software development, Jamie founded Japeto in 2014 to focus on AI in healthcare. He led the technical development of Pat, the UK's first sexual health chatbot, and helped build Japeto's conversational AI infrastructure. Jamie specializes in making conversational AI accessible and safe, particularly for sensitive applications.

Practitioners Hub testimonials

Ingrid Folland, CEO of Japeto AI: “As a small company, taking part in the Practitioners Hub suddenly entered us into conversations with government bodies and much larger organisations. It really opened our eyes to what others are doing in AI, and particularly around ethics. One of the big takeaways from the Practitioners Hub for me was the importance of being intentional about how you deploy AI – having a roadmap, thinking through the risks, and not just rushing into it.”

Madalena Alves dos Santos, Superintendent of Data and Results Management at the Department of Digital Transformation for the State of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil: “We’re trying to be pioneers here in our department, but often it feels like we’re doing it alone. Joining the Practitioners Hub helped us connect with others who are facing similar questions, in other countries and sectors. That’s incredibly important and valuable to us. A big lesson from the Practitioners Hub was that having good intentions is not enough. We need proper methodologies to show how we’re managing risks – especially in government, where accountability and transparency matter so much.”

Contributors and acknowledgements

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This case study is published under [The Turing Way Practitioners Hub 2024-25 Cohort - case study series](#). The Practitioners Hub is [The Turing Way](#) project that works with experts from partnering organisations to promote data science best practices. In 2024, *The Turing Way* team welcomed **Ingrid Follman, Jamie Tidman, Madalena Alves dos Santos, Beatriz Gomes de Souza,** and **José Hudson** as Experts in Residence to represent interests and opportunities across government services and ethical AI. We thank them for their participation in the Practitioners Hub and for leading the development of this case study.

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The Turing Way Practitioners Hub's 2024-25 Cohort was co-delivered by **Dr Malvika Sharan**, Senior Researcher - Open Research and **Arielle Bennett**, Senior Researcher - Open Source Practices. **Stuart Gillespie** is the technical editor for this case study. **Léllé Demertzi** is the Research Project Manager.

The Turing Way Practitioners Hub, designed and launched in 2023 by Dr Sharan, aims to accelerate the adoption of best practices. Through a six-month cohort-based program, the Hub facilitates knowledge sharing, skill exchange, case study co-creation, and the adoption of open science practices. It also fosters a network of 'Experts in Residence' across partnering organisations.

For any comments, questions or collaboration with *The Turing Way*, please email: turing-way@turing.ac.uk.

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